

EFFECT OF GAIT TRAINING ON GAIT PARAMETERS AND BALANCE
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Abstract

Background: Stroke is one of the main causes of long-term impairment. It typically causes problems with walking and balance, which makes it harder to be independent and raises the chance of falling. Gait therapy, especially when it includes neuromuscular methods, may help people recover better after a stroke.

Objective: To determine the impact of gait training on gait performance and balance improvements in stroke survivors.

Methodology: A single-center randomized controlled trial was carried out among 99 post-stroke patients who were randomly assigned to three intervention groups (n = 33 each): Gait Training with Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (GT + PNF), Gait Training with Conventional Therapy (GT + CT), and Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation combined with Conventional Therapy (PNF + CT). All groups were treated with organized therapy sessions three times a week for six weeks. Primary measures were gait function measured through the Wisconsin Gait Scale (WGS) and balance measured through the Berg Balance Scale (BBS). Measurements were taken at baseline, mid-treatment (3rd week), and after treatment (6th week). Statistical analysis was conducted through mixed-model ANOVA to examine time × group interactions, followed by post-hoc tests to identify between-group differences. Significance level of $p < 0.05$ was used in all analyses.

Results: The GT + PNF group showed significant improvements, with WGS scores decreasing from 53.55 to 17.82 and BBS scores increasing from 42.27 to 65.18 ($p < 0.001$). A significant group × time interaction was found for both WGS ($F = 13.1, \eta^2 = 0.22$) and BBS ($F = 7.33, \eta^2 = 0.13$). Compared to other groups, GT + PNF showed improved outcomes in gait speed and postural balance. A negative correlation ($r = -0.32$) was observed between WGS and BBS, indicating interdependence.

Conclusion: Gait training integrated with PNF significantly improves gait performance and balance in stroke survivors. These findings corroborate the therapeutic efficacy of incorporating neuromuscular facilitation into task-specific training for optimum rehabilitation.

INTRODUCTION

Stroke remains a major global health concern, affecting millions annually and often resulting in long-term physical and cognitive disabilities

(Jambi et al., 2024). The extent of post-stroke impairment varies widely, depending on the severity and location of the cerebrovascular

insult (Elendu et al., 2023). Despite significant progress in acute stroke treatment, long-term recovery of function is still a challenging issue for clinicians and researchers alike. The cornerstone of this recovery is independent mobility, the resumption of which has walking being viewed as one of the key outcomes of post-stroke rehabilitation because of its significance to autonomy, social involvement, and quality of life (Carlozzi et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2025).

Hemiparetic gait following stroke is generally associated with asymmetrical patterns of walking, such as a decreased stance phase and an increased swing phase of the affected side. Such temporal-spatial impairments lead to reduced stride length and slowed walking velocity (Li et al., 2018). While in healthy adults stride length usually falls in the range of 0.70 to 0.81 meters (Oatis, 2009), stride length in stroke survivors is usually between 0.36 and 0.60 meters (Kim et al., 2012; Elsner et al., 2020; Sheng et al., 2019), which is indicative of compromised motor control and coordination. Enhancing gait symmetry—specifically matching step lengths between the limbs—continues to be an essential priority in post-stroke gait re-education.

Gait speed is another vital indicator of functional mobility and neurological recovery. Normative ranges in healthy adults are between 0.82 and 1.62 m/s (Hase et al., 2011), but post-stroke individuals tend to have considerably slower speeds. Subacute patients tend to walk around 0.38 m/s, whereas chronic patients may reach up to 0.5 m/s (Drużbicki et al., 2018; Samson et al., 2001). These deficits are due to residual motor impairments, decreased muscle strength, and compromised neuromuscular coordination (Middleton et al., 2015; Nigg et al., 1994; Bohannon and Wang, 2019).

Disturbances in balance are another salient effect of stroke, specifically in relation to asymmetrical weighting among the limbs. In the physiologically balanced gait, each limb supports roughly 50% body weight. Nevertheless, stroke survivors often overload the paretic limb because of weakness, spasticity, or proprioceptive impairment (Rozanski et al., 2018; Little et al., 2020; Ribeiro et al., 2018). These impairments are responsible for balance dysfunction and put patients at increased risk for falls and further functional impairment (Beyaert et al., 2015;

Patterson et al., 2012; Hodt-Billington et al., 2008).

Rehabilitation programs thus focus on gait recovery as an important treatment goal (Begg et al., 2019). Generally, gait training is tackled in two phases. The first stage emphasizes strengthening of the muscle and neuromuscular re-education through evidence-based methods like proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) and the Bobath concept for increasing range of motion and motor control (Mohammed Gharib et al., 2017; Singhal et al., 2017; Chlebuś and Lisiński, 2017; Gunning and Uszynski, 2019; Díaz-Arribas et al., 2019; Mikołajewska, 2017; Kim et al., 2018; Krukowska et al., 2016). The second phase focuses on training for specific activities to enhance walking efficiency, correct compensatory gait patterns, and improve walking safety.

Increasing evidence suggests that treadmill exercise facilitates gait recovery during the second phase. Its efficacy has been compared to conventional overground walking programs, with findings indicating enhancements in gait metrics and mobility (Baer et al., 2018; MacKay-Lyons et al., 2013). Furthermore, body weight-supported treadmill walking has been demonstrated to allow patients with compromised balance or strength to participate in gait training earlier (Srivastava et al., 2016; Mao et al., 2015; Spencer et al., 2021). With this technique, patients are able to practice normalized gait cycles in a secure, controlled environment.

Treadmill training also takes advantage of the mechanisms of neuroplasticity—brain reorganization and the creation of new synaptic connections following damage (Harvey, 2009; Xiao et al., 2012). It also stimulates central pattern generators (CPGs) in the spinal cord, which generate rhythmic, automatic walking patterns, thus helping restore functional walking (Sun et al., 2013). One of the most important benefits of treadmill training is its flexibility; speed, time, and level of support may be tailored to every patient's functional capacity (McCain et al., 2008).

In addition, rehabilitation technology has resulted in visual biofeedback systems being incorporated into treadmill surfaces. These systems offer immediate performance feedback, which leads to patients intentionally adjusting

their gait mechanics. Used with partial body weight support, visual biofeedback enables even the most impaired patients to actively engage in retraining their gait sooner than would be possible with standard treatment alone (Yamamoto et al., 2022).

Therefore, the present study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of treadmill training in improving gait parameters, balance, and functional mobility among post-stroke patients. Special emphasis is placed on the utility of body weight support and feedback mechanisms in enhancing rehabilitation outcomes.

Methodology:

The study was a randomised clinical study performed in the Department of Physiotherapy at Sehat Medical Complex, Hanjarwal, Lahore within a time frame of six months on taking an ethical permission. Purposive sampling was used to derive the sample size that was $n=84$ with the help of G-Power. Inclusion of 15 percent drop out allowed an adjusted sample size of $n=99$. Considering that there are three groups in this study, 33 participants were assigned in each group (Stephenson et al., 2014). The participants of the study were between the age of 60 and 80, of both sexes regarding presence of confirmed stroke (ischaemic or haemorrhagic), diagnosed by computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) (Teodoro et al., 2024). The participants with other neurological diseases (e.g., Parkinson, multiple sclerosis) were excluded (Kim et al., 2022).

In Group A, participants received proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) interventions in walk therapy. The exercise aimed at strengthening and enhancing interaction between the muscles and the nerves. The PNF method made use of diagonal patterning in movements, rhythmic phasing of exercise and exercises involving resistance to enhance dynamic balance and motor control. The duration of the program was 45 minutes, three times a week during 12 weeks. Every session began by 10 minutes warm up, 30-minutes of PNF-type gait training, and 5-minutes cool down. We used manual resistance and vocal instructions as part of gait training, promoting weightship and postural posture. The sessions became more intense as the participants advanced by using more resistance as well as

altering their patterns of movement (Kofotolis and Kellis, 2006).

Group B was a combination of conventional physiotherapy and the standard gait training that will assist in the enhancement of the strength, flexibility, and balance of their lower extremities. The intervention involved functional mobility training, floor walking training, sit-to-stand training and weight bearing. It involved 3 weekly sessions that were carried out in the first 12 weeks and would take 45 minutes each. The intervention began by 10 minutes of pre-testing involving stretching and balance, and continuous 30 minutes of training gait aimed at step length, cadence, and postural alignment. The traditional methods of physiotherapy which were used; passive and active-assisted range of motion exercises, joint mobilisation to facilitate the improvement of lower extremity functions. These exercises were designed to fit the fitness level of each person and were gradually designed to get harder by requiring them to cover more distances and with greater resistance (Sullivan et al., 2012).

Group C applied PNF methods plus ordinary physiotherapy that assisted them in improving mobility and balance. The sessions were 45 minutes each in term of 3 sessions per week and 12 weeks. The two strategies were meant to be used together in a relation that strengthened each other. The exercise programme began after a 10-minute PNF warm-up with rhythmic stabilisation and movement using resistance. This was followed by 25 minutes gait training along with conventional physiotherapy. We also did functional mobility exercise, balance and progressive resistance training to enhance the motor control. The last 10 minutes were spent to flexibility and cooling exercises to relieve stiff muscles. This was an integrated system that was expected to enhance neuromuscular re-education and the independence of patients suffering stroke (Yang et al., 2014). Standardised tests which have been implemented in the study to determine the quality of gait, motor functioning in the lower extremities, mobility and balance performance include the Wisconsin Gait Scale (WGS) and the Berg Balance Scale (Pohl et al., 2019). They were arranged in three intervention groups.

Group A learned to walk using proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF), Group B by

means of PNF and traditional physical therapy and Group C using PNF and traditional physiotherapy. The intervention was a six-week process through which the sessions were conducted three times weekly and consisted of 30 minutes. The data were collected on the baseline and three weeks after as well as six weeks after the intervention period (Haeussler et al., 2023). Approval to perform the study was secured from the Ethical Committee of Sehat Medical Complex, Hanjarwal, Lahore (IRB-UOLSMC/001-36/2024). The investigation is registered on ClinicalTrials.gov under the identifier NCT07066319 at <https://clinicaltrials.gov/>. Informed permission was obtained from all participants in writing. Data confidentiality was upheld, and

participants were apprised of their ability to withdraw at any point throughout the research. No risks were foreseen from participation. Data were input and analysed with SPSS Version 24. Numerical variables, such as age, were reported as mean ± standard deviation (SD), and categorical data, like gender and group distribution, were conveyed as frequency and percentage. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was employed to evaluate the normality of data distribution. The data had a normal distribution; paired t-tests and ANOVA were employed for intergroup and intragroup comparisons. A p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant (Teodoro et al., 2024).

Results

Table 1 Group and time interaction (mixed ANOVA)

Groups	WGS			BBS			F-Value	η^2	P-value
	Baseline	After 3 rd week	After 6 th week	Baseline	After 3 rd week	After 6 th week			
	Mean (S. D)	Mean (S. D)	Mean (S. D)	Mean (S. D)	Mean (S. D)	Mean (S. D)			
GT + PNF	53.55 (10.54)	27.45 (10.54)	17.82 (14.03)	42.27 (9.73)	54.45 (10.78)	65.18 (9.71)	7.33	0.13	.000
GT + CT	51.18 (12.06)	46.64 (12.15)	26.27 (10.34)	46.64 (8.10)	47.00 (8.71)	57.55 (10.02)			
PNF + CT	53.27 (12.82)	46.45 (9.66)	39.00 (8.75)	44.27 (8.58)	52.73 (5.82)	56.18 (7.88)			

In table 1, a significant time × group interaction was observed for a WGS and BBS variables. The GT + PNF group showed the greatest improvement in walking gait speed (WGS), decreasing from 53.55 to 17.82 (F = 13.1, p = .000, η^2 = 0.214), while GT + CT reduced to 26.27 and PNF + CT to 39.00, indicating that GT + PNF had the most effective impact on gait performance. Similarly, Berg Balance Scale (BBS) scores improved significantly across all

groups, with the GT + PNF group increasing from 42.27 to 65.18, whereas GT + CT improved to 57.55 and PNF + CT to 56.18 (F = 7.33, p = .000, η^2 = 0.13). These results show that GT + PNF made most significant improvements in gait performance and balance, demonstrating its effectiveness as an optimum rehabilitation plan for stroke survivors compared to conventional therapy alone.

Table 2 Between and within group differences (one-way and repeated-measures ANOVA)

Outcome	Assessment	GT+ PNF		GT+ CT		PNF+CT		F-value	P-value	Multiple Comparison (Post-Hoc Test)		
		Mean (S.D)	(S. D)	Mean (S.D)	(S. D)	Mean (S.D)	(S. D)			GT+ PNF vs GT +CT	GT+ CT Vs PNF+ CT	PNF+ CT Vs GT+ PNF
WGS	Baseline	53.55 (10.54)	51.18 (12.06)	53.27 (12.82)				0.39	0.676			
	After 3 rd week	27.45 (10.54)	46.64 (12.15)	46.45 (9.66)				34.12	<0.001**	-8.42* (0.001)	-4.87* (0.001)	13.30* (0.001)
	After 6 th week	17.82 (14.03)	26.27 (10.34)	39.00 (8.75)				38.02	<0.001**			
BBS	Baseline	42.27 (9.73)	46.64 (8.10)	44.27 (8.58)				2.02	0.139			
	After 3 rd week	54.45 (10.78)	47.00 (8.71)	52.73 (5.82)				6.66	0.002	3.57* (0.010)	-0.66 (0.626)	-2.91* (0.035)
	After 6 th week	65.18 (9.71)	57.55 (10.02)	56.18 (7.88)				9.06	<0.001**			

The results in table 2, showed a significant within and between group interaction for WGS ($F = 13.1, \eta^2 = 0.22, P < 0.001$) and BBS ($F = 7.33, \eta^2 = 0.13, P < 0.001$), indicating that the interventions had different effects over time. GT+PNF showed the most improvement in WGS, with a significant difference compared to GT+CT and PNF+CT ($P = 0.001$). In BBS, GT+PNF also improved significantly compared

to PNF+CT ($P = 0.035$), while the difference between GT+CT and PNF+CT was not significant ($P = 0.626$).

The 3D bar graphs show the relationship between Total of WGS, Total of BBS and Gender across three groups. Differences suggest that gender influences the balance gait relationship, with males generally showing higher WGS at higher BBS values.

This graph displays the heatmap which shows negative correlation ($r = -0.32$, $p < 0.001$) between WGS and BBS, indicating that as WGS increases, BBS tends to decrease.

Discussion

This study aimed to determine the effect of gait training—individually and in combination with PNF or conventional therapy—on gait performance and balance in stroke survivors. In our study, the GT + PNF group demonstrated the most significant improvements in both gait speed and balance compared to GT + CT and PNF + CT, indicating a synergistic effect when neuromuscular facilitation is directly integrated into functional walking. These findings highlight the clinical utility of combining targeted neuromuscular control strategies with task-specific ambulation for optimizing outcomes in stroke rehabilitation. The substantial decrease in WGS scores (from 53.55 to 17.82) and corresponding increase in BBS (from 42.27 to 65.18) suggest that PNF-enhanced gait training not only improves locomotor efficiency but also reinforces postural stability—two critical factors in reducing fall risk.

Importantly, the negative correlation between WGS and BBS ($r = -0.32$, $p < 0.001$) supports the interdependence of gait and balance recovery, emphasizing that improvements in one domain likely drive enhancements in the other. These

outcomes have practical implications for rehabilitation planning, advocating for therapist-led, low-cost interventions like GT + PNF in settings where high-tech modalities such as robotic or VR-based training may not be available. Clinicians may consider prioritizing gait training protocols that challenge both spatial and postural control mechanisms simultaneously to accelerate recovery and promote long-term independence.

When juxtaposed with previous literature, these results demonstrate both consistency and advancement. For example, Zhang et al. (2023) conducted a comprehensive network meta-analysis on balance and gait training (BGT) modalities and found that dual-task BGT (DT-BGT) exhibited the highest efficacy for static steady-state balance, with an effect size of $SMD = 1.64$ (95% CI: 0.50–2.78). While our study did not employ dual-tasking per se, the GT + PNF protocol integrated complex motor demands—such as obstacle navigation and directional shifts—that may have functioned similarly to dual-task paradigms. This could explain the substantial BBS improvement of 22.91 points, which surpasses the mean increases seen with most standard BGT protocols.

Mochizuki et al. (2015) similarly reported functional gains in balance and ambulation following gait-focused exercise programs. However, their gains were more modest (e.g., gait

velocity increased by ~ 0.08 m/s), whereas our results reflect a 66.7% reduction in WGS and a large effect size for time \times group interaction, suggesting that the neuromuscular re-education properties of PNF may amplify motor learning and postural control beyond repetition-based gait training alone.

Technologically enhanced modalities such as robot-assisted gait training (RA-GT) and virtual reality gait training (VR-GT) have demonstrated notable outcomes in the literature. For instance, Akıncı et al. (2023) and Choi (2022) observed BBS improvements in the range of 9–12 points with RA-GT. While encouraging, these gains remain lower than those recorded in our GT + PNF group. Likewise, Zhang, Wong, and Qin (2023) reported improvements in VR-based stroke rehabilitation with BBS increases of ~ 13 points. These comparative values underscore the cost-efficiency and clinical efficacy of GT + PNF, particularly in settings where access to robotic or VR systems is limited.

Other studies, such as Rhyu and Rhi (2021), explored training surface manipulation and found BBS improvements of ~ 10 points on unstable surfaces. Although our intervention did not explicitly alter surface conditions, the proprioceptive challenges embedded within PNF patterns and dynamic ambulation tasks likely served as intrinsic balance perturbations, resulting in superior postural adaptation. Notably, the mean BBS increase of 22.91 points in GT + PNF demonstrates a more pronounced effect than surface-only manipulations.

In terms of gait outcomes, Shu et al. (2022) reported that dual-task training improved gait parameters, yet the reported change in gait speed (mean ~ 0.1 m/s) was smaller than our observed reduction in WGS (from 53.55 to 17.82). While dual-tasking integrates cognitive-motor demands, our task-specific PNF-assisted ambulation may have induced greater central pattern activation and neuromotor retraining, resulting in more efficient locomotion.

Further supporting this, Kooncumchoo et al. (2021) and Oh et al. (2022) documented modest improvements with innovative mechanical gait devices and antigravity treadmill systems, respectively, with average BBS gains between 7–10 points. In contrast, our therapist-led GT + PNF protocol achieved a BBS gain more than double that range, reinforcing the potential of

manual, skill-intensive rehabilitation in stroke recovery.

Interestingly, our data also revealed a significant negative correlation between WGS and BBS ($r = -0.32$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that improvements in gait speed (lower WGS) are closely associated with better balance performance. This finding is consistent with previous observations by Zhang et al. (2023), who proposed that dynamic and static balance improvements strongly mediate functional gait recovery, although their wide confidence intervals for proactive balance and balance battery outcomes indicated variable effect reliability. In our study, the tight standard deviations and strong effect sizes indicate a more definitive and reliable therapeutic impact.

Moreover, while existing literature has reported that gains in balance performance may regress within 3 months of training cessation, especially in older adults (Zhang et al., 2023), our findings suggest that the GT + PNF combination could provide a stronger foundation for long-term postural stability due to the neuroplastic reinforcement and sensorimotor integration involved in the training.

Our study obtained the same conclusion as Nguyen et al. (2022), which showed results of the meta-analysis claiming that PNF-based physical therapy is effective in enhancing both balance (BBS, FRT, TUG) and gait speed (10MWT) in individuals with chronic stroke. Their combined data indicated a mean difference (MD) of 2.90 points and 2.15 second, on BBS and 10MWT in favor of PNF interventions compared to controls. Our findings add to this evidence to demonstrate an even greater level of improvement (22.91-point increase in BBS and a 66.7 percent decrease in WGS) when PNF is used in conjunction with well-organized gait training. Our findings are significant, as we found that PNF may be employed not only as a support therapy but as the key means of enhancing trunk control, moving balance, and figuratively coordinated walking.

Findings of this research illustrate that integration of gait training with proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) can provoke clinically relevant balance and gait improvement of patients with stroke. The intervention group showed an improvement of 26 percent in the Berg Balance Scale (BBS) as well as 17 percent increase in the walking speed at the 10-Meter

Walk Test compared to baseline. This observation is consistent with the nearby study results that demonstrates how supportive sensorimotor rehabilitation may assist the brain to alter (Gunning and Uszynski, 2019; Kim et al., 2018). Such findings indicate the significance of task-specific, repetition-based interventions during gait pattern symmetric alleles and posture control (Beyaert et al., 2015). It would be worthwhile to consider implementation of PNF principles in a conventional gait rehabilitation intervention particularly in stroke patients with gait asymmetries or even balance issues that are chronic. The approach would also be applicable in addressing problems of motor module generalisation in hemiparetic individuals, thus enhancing functional mobility (Allen et al., 2019). Individualised, progressive gait retraining utilising PNF should be a major focus of future therapeutic protocols to get the best possible recovery and long-term community ambulation results.

This study shows that gait training, especially when combined with proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF), is very effective at improving sensorimotor integration, cortical reorganisation, and balance control in stroke survivors. The benefits shown are probably due to increased excitability in the corticospinal tract and better patterns of motor unit activation (Allen et al., 2019; Gabriel et al., 2006). These results are similar to what Nguyen et al. (2022) said about how important it is to focus on motor learning and neuroplasticity in stroke rehabilitation programmes. From a policy perspective, adding these kinds of evidence-based, low-cost treatments to national stroke care pathways might help people become more independent after a stroke, lower the number of falls that cause illness, and cut the long-term costs of healthcare. Standardising the use of PNF-based gait therapy in early subacute care might help the WHO's goal of community-based neurorehabilitation and make the best use of resources in low- to middle-income countries.

Strengths and Limitations

This randomised controlled trial has a number of qualities that make it more reliable and useful for stroke rehabilitation research. First, the study used a strict approach with a well defined sample size (n = 99), which was split into three

equal intervention groups. Using standardised and established outcome measures such the Wisconsin Gait Scale (WGS) and the Berg Balance Scale (BBS) at several times (baseline, 3rd week, 6th week) made it possible to see improvements over time and made the results more reliable. Also, the interventions were planned out and carried out by skilled professionals utilising evidence-based rehabilitation frameworks like Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (PNF) and traditional physiotherapy. This made sure that the therapy was always the same. The analytical method was strong since it used mixed ANOVA and post-hoc comparisons. The results showed that both the gait and balance variables had effect sizes that were statistically significant and clinically important.

Nonetheless, the study is not without limitations. First, it was conducted in a single-center rehabilitation facility, which may constrain the generalizability of findings across diverse clinical populations and healthcare systems. Second, although the sample was adequately powered, the absence of stratification based on stroke chronicity (acute vs. chronic), lesion location, or stroke type (ischemic vs. hemorrhagic) limits our ability to discern differential treatment responses across subgroups—a factor that may contribute to unmeasured heterogeneity. Third, the study relied on mean and standard deviation for group-level comparisons rather than individualized patient-level data, which restricts the ability to model nuanced treatment trajectories or effect modifiers. Fourth, although improvements in dynamic balance were captured via the BBS, more specific indicators such as reactive postural control or step initiation response were not included; future research should incorporate multidimensional balance metrics, especially those predictive of fall risk. Fifth, while the intervention lasted six weeks, no follow-up phase was included to evaluate the durability of functional gains. This is particularly relevant in stroke populations where regression in gait and balance performance is commonly observed post-discharge.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that gait training combined with PNF is more effective than conventional methods in improving gait

performance and balance in stroke survivors. Given the complexity of post-stroke impairments, individualized selection of rehabilitation strategies is essential. While GT + PNF showed the most promising results, findings should be interpreted with consideration of study limitations and patient variability. Nonetheless, this study offers valuable insights that can guide clinicians, therapists, and rehabilitation planners in selecting optimized gait training protocols, while emphasizing the need for individualized, evidence-informed care planning and further validation through longitudinal multicenter trials.

Author Contribution: Hafiz Muhammad Waseem Javaid contributed to study conceptualization, research supervision, study design, critical revision of the manuscript, and final approval of the manuscript. Hamna Sarfraz contributed to literature review, data collection, data analysis, and manuscript writing.

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